

Washing Effect on Fabrics Made of Cotton and its Blends with Modal and Tencel

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Abstract:

Natural fibers made from cellulosic materials are in constant demand owing to their beneficial properties. The climatic conditions of nature affect the production and supply of cotton fibers, which are both constrained. Regenerated fibers have been created to meet the demand for cotton fibers. Viscose fiber, a member of the first generation of regenerated cellulosic fibers, has a lower wet modulus than cotton. In order to address the shortcomings of first-generation cellulosic fibers and improve the qualities of the regenerated cellulose fiber, some modified cellulosic regenerated fibers, such as Modal and Tencel fibers, have been produced. The numerous washings could alter the physical structure of yarn and fabrics hence affecting the physical properties of the fabrics. In the present study, three types of fibrous materials: cotton, a blend of modal-cotton and tencel-cotton have been used to produce single jersey knitted fabrics and the effect of repeated washings on the physical properties (stitch density, fabric weight, fabric thickness, shrinkage and pilling) of knitted single jersey fabrics has been investigated. It has found that all three physical factors (stitch density, fabric weight and thickness), fabric shrinkage increase while pilling decreases drastically in the first two washing cycles thereafter little change has been observed in further washing cycles. Pilling has good correlation with all three physical factors but shrinkage shows good correlation with stitch density only.

Keywords: Dimensional stability, Pilling Modal, repeated washings, Shrinkage, Tencel

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1. Introduction

In the present competitive textile market, to survive and also establish themselves as market leaders, textile manufacturers are searching for new products with improved properties to enhance the value and versatility of the product [1]. Cotton fibres provide good quality to the fabric but have low production [2]. Because to limited availability of cotton fibres, some regenerated cellulosic fibres have been developed, but these first-generation regenerated fibres have low wet-modulus. To overcome the drawback of the first-generation cellulosic regenerated fibres, some modified fibres have been developed in which the Modal[®] and Tencel[®] LF are two important cellulosic regenerated fibres manufactured by Lenzing Company, Austria [3, 4]. These are new developments of viscose rayon and are considered high wet modulus fibres.

The scope of knitted fabrics is increasing rapidly, especially in sportswear and leisurewear [5, 6]. This is due to some positive qualities such as softness, flexibility and moisture absorption, etc. The new generation is very fond of knitted fabrics. The properties of a fabric mostly depend upon constituent raw material (chemical nature and fibre morphology), yarn structure, and fabric structure. The structure of fabric is governed by physical factors such as stitch density, fabric weight and thickness [7, 8]. Mostly, cotton yarn is used to produce knitted fabrics, but a blend of cotton with Modal and Tencel can also be used to develop some special properties.

Both shrinkage and pilling behavior affect the serviceability of garments [9]. Shrinkage affects the dimensional stability of a fabric and leads to a large number of customer complaints. In comparison to other faults such as poor abrasion resistance, dimensional change can appear early in the life of a garment, so making a complaint more likely. Fabric shrinkage can cause problems in two main areas, either during garment manufacture or during subsequent laundering by the end user. Pilling is a surface defect of textiles that arises in wear due to the formation of small 'pills' of entangled fibre giving it an ugly appearance. Pills are formed by rubbing action on loose fibres which are present on the fabric surface.

Dimensional stability of a fabric is an important issue for both consumers as well as fabric manufactures because unacceptable dimensional change is often the main reason for product rejection by the consumer [1, 10, 11]. Garment requires several washings in its lifetime. During washing, the garment is subjected to complex mechanical, thermal and chemical actions that may alter the fabric structure such as shrinkage (hence stitch density), fabric thickness and fabric weight (GSM), which ultimately change the fabric properties and performance [11, 12]. The knitted fabric may easily alter its structure after repeated washings. The changes in structure of fabric may depend upon the type of fibrous material and number of washings.

In a previous study on cotton fabric [10], the effect of repeated washings (in four steps: 4-wash, 8-wash, 12-wash and 16-wash) on cotton woven fabric properties: fabric physical factors and dimensional stability was analyzed. It was found that after repeated washing, the fabric cover factor, fabric thickness, fabric weight and fabric shrinkage increased and this increased abruptly in the first step (of four washes) and thereafter slightly changed. In another study [3], the effect of wet processing on the comfort and mechanical properties of woven fabrics made using yarns of cotton fibres and their blend with modal and tencel fibres in weft was studied. In an extended study [7], models have also been developed to predict the comfort and mechanical properties through three structural parameters (cover factor, fabric weight and fabric thickness) of woven fabrics. There is lack of study, which give clear view about the impact of repeated washings on dimensional stability and pilling behavior of knitted fabric made from 100 % cotton, cotton-modal blend and cotton Tencel blend fibres.

The aim of the present study is to analyze the effect of repeated washings on the physical properties of single jersey knitted fabrics made using 100% cotton fibre yarn, 50:50% cotton-modal blend and 50:50% cotton-tencel blend yarns. The study is focused on the investigation of the fabrics for their physical factors (stitch density, GSM and thickness), dimensional stability and pilling behavior as these are important properties for any garment.

2. Material and Method

2.1 Material

Three types of plain knit single jersey fabrics were prepared by using ring spun yarns of 100% cotton fibres, 50:50% cotton-modal, and 50:50% cotton-tencel blended yarns. The above fabric samples were washed in four steps: 0-wash, 2-wash, 4-wash and 6-wash. Thus, total 12 samples were made. The details of the raw materials used for making the samples are given in Table 1. The processes involved for making the samples is depicted in Figure 1.

Table 1: Detail of raw materials

S. No.	Information	Cotton	Modal	Tencel
1	Type of fibre	Natural	Natural	Manmade
2	Generic name	Cotton- combed	Cotton- combed	Lyocell-Tencel® LF
3	Material type	J-34 (Punjab), S-6 (Gujrat)	J-34 (Punjab), S-6 (Gujrat)	Lenzing AG
4	Nature of fibre	Cellulosic fibre	Cellulosic fibre	Regenerated cellulosic fibre
5	Avg. length and fineness	28.5 mm, 4.4 mic	28.5 mm, 4.4 mic	38 mm, 1.2 den
6	Moisture regain (%)	8.5	8.5	11
7	Dry Tenacity cN/tex (gpd)	29 (3.2)	29 (3.2)	38 (4.3)
8	Wet Tenacity cN/tex (gpd)	32 (3.6)	32 (3.6)	29 (3.2)
1	Elongation % (Dry/Wet)	6.8/8.1	6.8/8.1	14/16

Figure 1: Flow chart of processes for making samples

Two varieties of cotton, J-34 and S-6, were mixed in a 50:50 ratio at mixing stage to produce 100% combed cotton yarn. The mixed cotton is processed through blow room, carding, draw frame (auto-leveler), Unilap comber, draw frame (breaker), draw frame (finisher), speed frame, ring frame and autoconer (Figure 1). Modal® and Tencel® fibres were blended each with cotton fibres in 50:50 ratio at drawing stage after combing to make the modal-cotton and tencel-cotton blended yarns respectively. For the production of blended yarns; the modal and tencel fibres were processed each through the blowroom and carding, blended with a combed cotton sliver (which was made for 100% cotton yarn) at the drawing stage giving two processes (breaker and finisher heads), speed frame, ring frame and autoconer [3]. The nominal yarn count and TPI of the yarn were kept 30s (Ne) and 20 respectively. Three types of plain weft knitted single jersey fabrics were made using each 100% cotton yarn, 50-50% cotton-modal yarn and 50-50% cotton-tencel yarn on a 20-gauge circular knitting machine having a 24-inch machine diameter. The courses and wales per centimeter are kept 30 each.

To study the impact of repeated washings, each fabric sample underwent repeated washings in four stages, i.e. 0-wash, 2-wash, 4-wash and 6-wash. The concept of taking steps of two laundering cycles is because a single laundering cycle may not give significant results for comparison. The samples were laundered at 20°C in a semi-automatic washing machine using 0.8 g/l solution of non-ionic detergent-Ellen-N-100 (96% concentration). One laundering cycle was completed in 38 minutes. The samples were dried in open space in daylight. Finally, a total of 12 fabric samples were prepared for the study.

2.2 Methods

The physical factors: stitch density, GSM and thickness, dimensional stability and pilling behavior of the fabric samples were analyzed. Prior to the test, the samples were conditioned at 65±2 percent relative humidity and 27±2°C temperature as per IS: 6359:1971(re-affirmed 2004) [13].

The courses per inch (CPI) and wales per inch (WPI) were determined as per ASTM D8007-15(2019) [14] and the stich density is the product of these two parameters. Fabric weight in grams per square meter (GSM) was measured as per ASTM D3776 [15] Fabric thickness is defined as perpendicular distance between the upper and lower sides of the fabric. It was measured with the help of precision fabric thickness tester as per ASTMD1777-96 (2019) [16].

Dimensional stability of a fabric is a measure of the extent to which it keeps its original dimensions subsequent to its manufacture. It was determined in terms of areal shrinkage as per BS:4931-1986[17]. 30 cm x 30 cm fabric samples were taken for the test. The samples were marked with three sets of lines in each direction, a minimum of 250 mm apart and at least 25 mm from all edges. Areal shrinkage was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Areal shrinkage \%} = \frac{\text{Area of 0 wash fabric} - \text{Area of n wash fabric}}{\text{Area of 0 wash fabric}} \times 100$$

Fabric pilling behavior of the samples was determined with the help of a standard Fabric Pilling Tester as per BIS standard (IS: 10971) [18]. A specimen of 125 mm x 125 mm was cut from fabric (3 each, of course-wise and wale-wise). Stitched face-to-face and turned inside out. The fabric tube was then mounted on rubber tubes. The loose ends were taped with PVC tape. All the four samples were then tumbled together in a cork-lined box 9" x 9" x 9" and rotated at 60 rev/min for five hours. The specimens were taken out and removed from a rubber tube and rated for pilling. Grading was done between 1 and 5. Higher grade exhibits higher pilling resistant fabric i. e. lesser pilling.

3. Result & Discussion

The test results for various fabric samples of 4-steps of washings (0-wash, 2-wash, 4 wash and 6 wash) in physical factors (GSM, stich density and thickness), Service properties (areal shrinkage, and pilling), are tabulated in Table 2 impact of repeated washings are shown in Figure. 3-8. The results are statistically analyzed upto 95 % significance limit.

Table 2: Physical factors and fabric properties

Blend	100% Cotton				Cotton-Modal				Cotton-Tencel			
	0-Wash	2-Wash	4-Wash	6-Wash	0-Wash	2-Wash	4-Wash	6-Wash	0-Wash	2-Wash	4-Wash	6-Wash
No of washings												
Stitch density/inch ²	965.3	1094.0	1105.8	1116.0	940.8	1061.6	1083.6	1095.2	855.6	1029.9	1041.2	1071.6
GSM	104.3	120.0	121.0	121.7	92.3	109.0	110.0	110.7	087.6	96.3	101.6	102.3
Thickness (mm)	0.51	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.42	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.42	0.47	0.48	0.48
Areal Shrinkage (%)	0.00	11.39	12.66	12.66	0.00	15.39	17.07	17.07	0.00	16.46	17.35	17.35
Pilling (Grade)	3.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.0

i. Fabric physical factors

Fabric physical factors such as stitch density, GSM and fabric thickness also affect the various fabric properties. The test results are tabulated in table 3 and fabric physical factors are determined as under:

a. Stitch density

Stitch density is a product of two parameters: courses/inch and wales/inch and expressed in stitch density per square inch. Fig.-2 shows that the stitch density increases sharply in the first step of two washes; this is because in first stage of washings, the shrinkage is more and thereafter, very less shrinkage takes place. After the first step of two washes, a slight increase in stitch density can be seen upto 6-wash in all samples. In all steps of washing, the stitch density of cotton sample is the highest, followed by cotton-modal blend and cotton-tencel blend fabric samples.

Figure 2: Effect of repeated washings on stitch density

b. Fabric weight (GSM)

Measured fabric weight of all samples in terms of grams per square meter (GSM) is presented in Table 3. The effect of repeated washings in fabric samples made using 100 % cotton yarn, 50:50 Cotton-Modal blended yarn and 50:50

Cotton-Tencel blended yarn is shown in Fig. 3. The figure exhibits that the fabric weight of all three types of samples increases significantly in the first step of 2-washes and after that there is no significant change has seen in all the samples. It may be due to fabric shrinkage more at first step of two washes which affect the stitch density, hence fabric weight. In all the fabrics, GSM of cotton fabric is the highest, followed by cotton-modal blend and cotton-tencel blend fabrics.

Figure 3: Effect of repeated washings on Fabric weight

c. Fabric thickness.

The impact of repeated washings on each fabric sample is shown in Fig. 4. The fabric thickness of all three samples increases significantly upto first step of two washing cycles and after that there is almost no change was observed. The reason is again the same, i.e. in the first step of two washing, it shrinks more due to fabric relaxation. The fabric thickness of the 100% cotton sample is the highest among all fabric samples, while cotton-modal and cotton-tencel samples are almost the same.

Figure 4: Effect of repeated washings on thickness of fabric

ii. Dimensional stability

Dimensional stability is measured in terms of areal shrinkage; more areal shrinkage means less dimensionally stable fabric. The test results are given in Table 2 and the impact of repeated washings is shown in Fig. 5. The areal shrinkage of all the three types of samples increases sharply on the first step of two washes (due to fabric relaxation). Afterwards, the increase is very small in further washing cycles. The areal shrinkage of the cotton-tencel blend is observed highest among all the samples, followed by the cotton-modal blend and 100% cotton fabric. That means, 100% cotton fabric shows the highest dimensional stability, followed by cotton-modal blended fabric and cotton-tencel blend, during repeated washings. There was no significant difference found in the areal shrinkage of both cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blended fabric samples. The shrinkage of fabrics depends upon the nature of raw material and fabric physical factors such as stitch density, GSM and fabric thickness. The cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blended fabric's areal shrinkage is approximately similar in all washing-steps and has no significant differences. Table 3 shows that the areal shrinkage has good correlation ($R=0.81$) with stitch density but poor correlation with fabric weight and fabric thickness. This is because various raw materials have different physical and chemical structures which may affect shrinkage behavior of the fibrous materials.

Figure 5: Effect of repeated washings on areal shrinkage of fabric

Table 3: Correlation between fabric physical factors and properties

Fabric physical factors	Correlation (R-value) with fabric properties	
	Areal shrinkage	Pilling
Stitch density	0.81	-0.86
GSM	0.44	-0.87
Thickness	0.32	-0.83

ii. Pilling resistance

The data for pilling resistance grade is presented in Table 2 and the effect of pilling is illustrated in Fig. 6. The pilling resistance grades decrease drastically up to the first step of two washes in comparison to the unwashed knitted fabric samples. After two washes, there is no change observed in the pilling resistance in further washed samples. The pilling resistance of the cotton-modal blend and cotton-tencel blended fabric is the same and is much higher than that of the 100% cotton sample. That means the cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blend fabrics have less tendency to pill than 100% cotton fabric. Pilling resistance shows good correlation (Table 3) with stitch density ($R = -0.86$), fabric weight ($R = -0.87$) and thickness ($R = -0.83$). These parameters have an inverse relation with pilling, i.e. if fabric stitch density or GSM or thickness increases, the pilling resistance decreases.

Figure 6: Effect of repeated washings on pilling resistance grades of fabric

In an overall evaluation of all three samples in respect to pilling resistance behavior and dimensional stability (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6), it was found that cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blended fabric exhibit higher pilling resistance but less dimensionally stable than cotton fabric.

4. Conclusion

Results reveals that maximum areal shrinkage took place in the first step of two washes in all three types of fabric samples. After the first step of washing, shrinkage increases slowly. Among all samples, the shrinkage of cotton-tencel blended fabric sample has highest areal shrinkage followed by cotton-modal blended and 100% cotton

fabrics. The areal shrinkage in cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blended fabric samples is almost similar in all washing steps and has no significant differences. The areal shrinkage has good correlation with stitch density.

Pilling resistance decreases significantly in first step of two-washing cycles, nevertheless no further change is observed. The pilling resistance of cotton-modal blended and cotton-tencel blended fabric samples is the same and is much higher than that of a 100% cotton sample. That means the cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blended fabrics have much less tendency to pill than 100% cotton fabric. Pilling resistance has good correlation with stitch density, fabric weight and thickness. In an overall evaluation, it was found that cotton-modal and cotton-tencel blended fabric exhibit higher pilling resistance behavior but less dimensionally stable than cotton fabric.

The research findings will help to fabric manufactures, researchers and end users. Furthermore, an extensive study will require on various comfort and hand properties in future.

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